
Physical Facilities, Service Quality, Human Resource Competence, and Service Satisfaction (A Study of Logistics Facilities at the Financial Services Authority Head Office) FRONT

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency on satisfaction of logistics facility services for internal customers at the Financial Services Authority (OJK) Head Office, Jakarta. This study is motivated by the importance of providing effective logistics facility services in supporting the implementation of operational activities and organizational performance. The study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method. Data were collected through distributing questionnaires to 356 OJK employees at the Head Office as users of logistics facility services and analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 software. The results of hypothesis testing indicate that physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency have a positive and significant effect on service satisfaction. Simultaneously, the three independent variables have a significant effect on service satisfaction with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.635, which indicates that 63.5% of the variation in service satisfaction can be explained by physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency, while the remaining 36.5% is influenced by other factors outside this study. Physical facilities are the variable with the greatest influence on service satisfaction compared to other independent variables. Research findings indicate that continuous improvement of physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency is necessary to enhance service satisfaction among logistics facility users within the OJK Head Office.

1. Introduction

Logistics facility services within the OJK organization are one of the main tasks of the Logistics Department, as outlined in the Regulation of the Board of Commissioners of the

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The logistics facility service function at the OJK is carried out by the Logistics Department, which is under the auspices of the Strategic Management Division. (Hax & Majluf, 1984), "Strategic management is a method for directing a company in achieving various goals, which includes institutional values and obligations, as well as administrative procedures related to operational and strategic decision-making at several levels of hierarchy and managerial competence.

Strategic management can be defined as a series of important actions and choices implemented by senior management and implemented by all members of an organization. Its goal is to achieve and realize the institution's vision and mission. Within an institution, there is a department responsible for strategic management, as is the case at the Financial Services Authority (OJK). The OJK's Strategic Management Division has targets to be achieved from several perspectives: the strategic support perspective, the internal process perspective, and the stakeholder perspective. (OJK, 2014).

In this case, the Logistics Department is one of the work units with an important role in the strategic support perspective at OJK which is responsible for providing, managing, ensuring the smooth and reliable provision of logistics needs to support operations in various work units within the OJK environment.

Entering the 13th year of OJK's existence, the Logistics Department continues to strive to continuously improve its performance, pursuing and implementing various innovation efforts in every business process. In carrying out its duties, the OJK Logistics Department is faced with various challenges in managing operational risk and improving logistics performance. Poorly managed operational risk can impact logistics performance from a strategic support perspective and OJK's overall operations within the strategic management function.

OJK has an organizational structure consisting of 11 (eleven) fields (DOSM OJK, SIMFOSIA, 2023), 9 (nine) of which carry out operational functions with 18 (eighteen) Work Units under them. All of these work units are divided into OJK at the head office which includes 46 (forty-six) Departments and in the regions which include 9 (nine) Class A OJK Offices, 5 (five) Class B OJK Offices and 21 (twenty-one) Class C OJK Offices.

The number of OJK employees has grown significantly since its inception in 2013, with 3,208 employees at the head office (74.26%) and 1,112 employees at regional offices (25.74%). This demonstrates the growing need for logistics services to support OJK's operational activities, all of which require well-governed logistics management.

Logistics is a function related to the arrangement of movement, coordination of product movement, and management of material storage from the initial sender through the entire supply chain until it reaches the final customer destination. (Walters, 2003) This function encompasses several operations related to planning, executing, and regulating the movement of commodities, materials, and information. Logistics is crucial to ensuring that goods or services are delivered to clients on time, in optimal condition, and at a cost-effective price.

Logistics encompasses tasks such as procurement, inventory management, transportation, warehouse management, distribution, and product safety and quality control. Its goal is to ensure the smooth and efficient flow of the entire supply chain, from procurement to final delivery to customers. Through effective logistics, companies can optimize their operations, reduce costs, increase customer satisfaction, and support sustainable business growth.

Logistics is a strategically designed procedure for overseeing the procurement, transportation, and storage of materials, components, and finished goods, as well as the associated information flow, within an organization's marketing network. The goal is to achieve optimal company profits, both in the current and future periods, in the most efficient manner. (Christopher, 2011). The logistics process is designed to ensure timely delivery of goods or services to clients, ensuring they are in optimal condition and at a reasonable cost.

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Logistics encompasses the planning, execution, and control of the movement of materials, information, and other related resources essential to a company's operations. This includes inventory management, shipping, product quality monitoring, and workflow optimization. Through an efficient and strategic logistics approach, companies can increase their competitiveness, reduce production and distribution costs, and better meet customer needs.

The role of the Logistics Department at OJK as regulated in Regulation of the Board of Commissioners of the Financial Services Authority of the Republic of Indonesia No. 2/PDK.02/2024 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Regulation of the Board of Commissioners of the Financial Services Authority No. 1/PDK.02/2023 concerning the Organization of the Financial Services Authority, is preparation of logistics policies and provisions, logistics planning and monitoring, development, preparation and management of logistics activity implementation systems for the transformation of logistics functions, planning and procurement of goods and/or services, including strategic goods and/or services infrastructure, implementation of supplier selection, asset management, provision of logistics support and facilities, security and correspondence and archiving.

Operational activities within the OJK Head Office interact with various organizational activities involving stakeholders and represent OJK as an organization. Internally, from June 2021 to June 2023, there were: 2000 internal correspondence related to the logistics facility services of the Logistics Department (SIPENA OJK, June 2023).

Several studies have shown that factors influencing service satisfaction depend on the level of need or importance. One such study (Setiawan H., 2014) shows that service quality, perceived value, trust, and customer satisfaction have a strong and influential effect on bank customer loyalty. Research on Logistics Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction: Evidence from Salalah Port, Oman was conducted on users of port logistics services at the Port of Salalah, Oman, using the SERVQUAL TERRA model approach (tangibles, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and assurance). It shows a positive and significant influence of all service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction. (Sukati I., Husda, Wangdra, Suhardi, & Realize, 2024) The results of this study indicate that logistics service quality, supported by physical infrastructure, service accuracy, timeliness, and service capability, significantly influences customer satisfaction. This study, although focused on external consumers, is relevant to the current research because of its emphasis on SERVQUAL-based logistics services. Other studies have shown that service quality and technology implementation have a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction. (Santo, John Edward, & Simon, 2022). In addition, customer satisfaction has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty, while customer value substantially increases customer satisfaction. However, customer perception has a positive but not significant impact on customer loyalty. Furthermore, the final research findings confirm that service quality, technology implementation, and customer evaluation are crucially related and have a causal relationship with loyalty through customer satisfaction.

From the perspective of internal customers, satisfaction plays a crucial role in an organization. (Tung & Wan-Jing, 2010) The results show that various HR competencies correlate with internal customer satisfaction and organizational efficiency. Practitioners should modify and prioritize specific HR processes and highlight the importance of internal customers in improving organizational performance. These results underscore the importance of internal customers in improving employee morale, organizational commitment, productivity, employee turnover rates, and the organization's ability to recruit talent.

Customer satisfaction is a form of comparative results of benefits experienced with benefits that were initially estimated.(Kurniawan & Soliha, 2022)The findings of this study indicate that service quality, facilities, and location have a positive effect on customer satisfaction. The study population included customers who made purchases at My Kopi O Semarang, with a sample size of 100 respondents.(probability sampling method), using a multiple regression analysis approach. This study refers to the SERVQUAL Service Quality theory, which is based on the premise that service quality emphasizes efforts to meet customer desires and expectations, as well as the accuracy of delivery that aligns with customer expectations. In similar research(Era, Ares, & Fitri, 2022), it is said that in the context of competition, business actors are required to be able to satisfy customers by creating quality products or services that meet consumer expectations. Customer satisfaction depends not only on the provision of high-quality goods, but also on the quality of services provided by the company. The quality of services and facilities is an important element in ensuring customer satisfaction. This study uses a quantitative approach, using multiple linear regression analysis on 102 respondents, and shows the partial impact of service quality, the partial impact of facilities, and the simultaneous impact of services and facilities on customer satisfaction.

Fast and accurate service, supported by reliable personnel, accompanied by the ability to provide reliable explanations and keep physical facilities clean, well-maintained and safe, can guarantee client happiness.(Mochamad, Wilis, & Yuliantoro, 2023)The results of the study show a positive and significant influence of service quality and physical facilities, both partially and simultaneously, on customer satisfaction. In the Logistics Facilities Section of the OJK Logistics Department, there are no clear parameters related to the level of customer satisfaction (internal) for the Logistics Facilities Section. There are various perceptions regarding the results of the services provided. There is no clear limit on when a logistics facility service can be declared complete, well-delivered, or conversely considered a failure and of poor quality. As a result, assessments of the services provided are often based on the subjective perceptions and experiences of each user. This study aims to analyze the influence of physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency on service satisfaction for internal customers (Study on Logistics Facilities Services at the Financial Services Authority Head Office), based on several previous studies. This study differs from previous studies because it uses a different sample of objects and combines several independent variables that were examined separately in previous studies. in several studies, namely physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency with reference to the main dimensions of SERVQUAL theory.

2. Methods

This study uses data obtained through a questionnaire using a cross-sectional method, or a longitudinal method, over a specific period of time. This study uses quantitative techniques, using a survey for data collection and a questionnaire as a variable measurement instrument. The questionnaire was carefully designed, considering previous research and its relevance to the SERVQUAL theory used in this study. The questionnaire will be answered by OJK employees at the OJK Head Office as internal customers in the Logistics Facility Services Section of the OJK Logistics Department. This is intended to ensure that the information obtained can provide an in-depth understanding of the study variables. Study This This is a causality study (explanatory), Because test The relationship between variables to determine whether a variable occurs, is influenced by, or is produced by another variable. The main objective is to analyse and explain the impact of user experience on the quality of logistics services. The research objects are OJK employees within the OJK Head Office as users (internal customers) of the OJK Logistics Department's logistics facility services. The objects will be taken from employees of non-Logistics Department work units within the OJK head office who use the logistics facility services.

3. Results and Discussion

Hypothesis Testing

Partial Effect Test (t-Test)

The t-test is intended to determine how far the influence of one independent variable (Physical Facilities, Service Quality and HR Competence) individually in explaining the dependent variable (Service Satisfaction), the testing criteria with a significance level (α) = 0.05 are determined as follows:

Table 1.
Partial Effect Test (t-Test)
Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.878	.807		-1,087	.278
	Physical Facilities	.502	.055	.367	9,209	.000
	Quality of Service	.343	.042	.316	8,157	.000
	HR Competence	.414	.046	.325	9,081	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Service Satisfaction

Source: 2026 Respondent Data Processing

Based on the table above, the following is stated:

- Variable X1 (Physical Facilities) has a significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) so that the Physical Facilities variable (X1) has a significant effect on Service Satisfaction (Y).
- Variable X2 (Service Quality) has a significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) so that the Service Quality variable (X2) has a significant effect on Service Satisfaction (Y).
- Variable X3 (HR Competence) has a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) so that the HR Competence variable (X3) has a significant effect on Service Satisfaction (Y).

Simultaneous Effect Test (F Test)

The simultaneous influence test F was conducted to determine the influence of independent variables (Physical Facilities, Service Quality and HR Competence) together or simultaneously on the dependent variable (Service Satisfaction).

Table 2.
Simultaneous Effect Test (F Test)
ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1691,883	3	563,961	203,707	.000b
	Residual	974,507	352	2,768		
	Total	2666.390	355			

a. Dependent Variable: Service Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), HR Competence, Service Quality, Physical Facilities

Source: 2026 Respondent Data Processing

From the results of the ANOVA test or F test above, a significance value of 0.000 was obtained. Because the significance value is smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), it can be said that the independent variables (Physical Facilities, Service Quality and HR Competence) simultaneously or together have a significant effect on the dependent variable (Service Satisfaction).

Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

Table 3.
Test of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.797a	.635	.631	1.66388

a. Predictors: (Constant), HR Competence, Service Quality, Physical Facilities

b. Dependent Variable: Service Satisfaction

Source: 2026 Respondent Data Processing

From the table above, it can be seen that the R value obtained is 0.797. This indicates that the correlation or relationship between the independent variables (Physical Facilities, Service Quality and HR Competence) with the value of the dependent variable (Service Satisfaction) is included in the Strong category. The resulting R² coefficient of determination is 0.635. This means that 63.5% of the variation in Service Satisfaction can be explained by the independent variables (Physical Facilities, Service Quality and HR Competence) used in the regression equation. While the remaining 36.5% is explained by other variables outside this study.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing using multiple linear regression analysis with the SPSS version 25 application, the results obtained were that all independent variables in this study, namely physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competence, had a significant influence on satisfaction with logistics facility services at the OJK Head Office.

Table 4.
Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Hypothesis Statement	Results
H1	Physical facilities have a positive and significant influence on satisfaction with logistics facility services in the OJK Head Office environment.	Accepted
H2	Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Service Satisfaction of logistics facilities in the OJK Head Office environment.	Accepted
H3	Human resource competency has a positive and significant influence on satisfaction with logistics facility services at the OJK Head Office.	Accepted

Source: 2026 Respondent Data Processing

Based on the partial test results (t-test), all independent variables had a significance value less than 0.05, thus all research hypotheses were accepted. Furthermore, based on the simultaneous test results (F-test), physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency jointly had a significant effect on satisfaction with logistics facilities at the OJK Head Office. These results indicate that the better the physical facilities, service quality, and HR competency, the higher the level of satisfaction with logistics facility services within the OJK Head Office.

4. Discussion

The Influence of Physical Facility Variables on Satisfaction with Logistics Facility Services

The results of the study indicate that the physical facility variable has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction with logistics facility services within the OJK Head Office. This is evidenced by the results of the t-test which shows a significance value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05 with a regression coefficient value of 0.502. Thus, the first hypothesis (H1) is declared accepted. The results of this study indicate that the better the condition of the physical facilities provided by the OJK Logistics Department, the higher the level of service satisfaction felt by internal service users. Physical facilities that are clean, comfortable, adequate, and able to support employee work activities are important factors in forming a positive perception of logistics facility services.

Furthermore, the standardized beta coefficient of 0.367 indicates that physical facilities are the variable with the greatest relative influence on service satisfaction compared to other independent variables. This indicates that users of OJK's internal services place a high premium on the comfort of facilities and support for work facilities to support the effectiveness of daily operational activities. This research finding aligns with the SERVQUAL theory. (Pasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml, 1988), especially in the tangible dimension which explains that physical evidence of services such as facilities, infrastructure and service environment are an important part in forming perceptions of service quality and user satisfaction.

The results of this study are also in line with research which states that physical facilities in logistics services have an influence on user satisfaction. (Sukati I., Husda, Wangdra, Suhardi, & Realize, 2024) The research results indicate that adequate physical facilities can improve service effectiveness and enhance positive user experiences. In the context of the Financial Services Authority (OJK), good physical facilities help employees carry out their work activities more effectively, thereby increasing satisfaction with the logistics services provided by the Logistics Department.

The Influence of Service Quality Variables on Satisfaction with Logistics Facility Services

The results of the study indicate that the service quality variable has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction with logistics facilities at the OJK Head Office. This is evidenced by the t-test results, which show a significance value of 0.000, less than 0.05, with a regression coefficient value of 0.343. Thus, the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

The results of this study indicate that the quality of service provided by the OJK Logistics Department can influence the level of satisfaction of internal service users. Timeliness of service, speed of response, reliability of service, and consistency of service are important factors in supporting user satisfaction of logistics facilities.

Although the service quality variable has a significant influence on service satisfaction, the standardized beta coefficient value of 0.316 indicates that the effect of service quality is the smallest compared to other independent variables. These results indicate that in the context of OJK's internal services, physical facilities and employee competence have a relatively greater influence than service quality on service user satisfaction.

The findings of this study are in line with the SERVQUAL theory, especially in the dimensions of reliability and responsiveness, which explains that the quality of the service process is an important factor in shaping user satisfaction. (Pasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml, 1988). The results of this study are also in line with research *The Influence of Service Quality and Customer Value on Customer Satisfaction* (Fauzi & Purnomo, 2023) which shows that service quality has a positive relationship with service user satisfaction.

In the context of OJK's internal services, fast, accurate, reliable, and responsive service quality helps support the smooth running of employee work activities, thereby increasing satisfaction with the logistics facility services provided by the Logistics Department.

The Influence of Human Resource Competency Variables on Satisfaction with Logistics Facility Services

The results of the study indicate that human resource competency variables have a positive and significant effect on satisfaction with logistics facility services at the OJK Head Office. This is evidenced by the t-test results, which show a significance value of 0.000, less than 0.05, with a regression coefficient of 0.414. Therefore, the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted.

The results of this study indicate that the competency of OJK Logistics Department employees plays a crucial role in improving internal user satisfaction. Employees' ability to provide professional, communicative, and responsive service, while understanding user needs, are factors that influence satisfaction levels with logistics facilities.

In addition, the standardized coefficient beta value of 0.325 indicates that HR competence is a variable that has a relatively large influence on service satisfaction and is ranked second after physical facilities. This indicates that employee competence is an important factor in shaping the quality of an organization's internal services. The findings of this study are in line with the assurance dimension in the SERVQUAL theory which emphasizes the importance of competence, ability, knowledge, and trust in the service process. (Pasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml, 1988).

The results of this study are also in line with research (Lin, Ling, Liu, & Hu, 2021) which shows that the quality of internal services and employee competence have an influence on the quality of services and the satisfaction of users of the organization's internal services. In the context of the OJK, the competence of Logistics Department employees is an important factor in supporting the effectiveness of logistics facility services so as to increase employee satisfaction as users of internal services within the OJK Head Office environment.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research regarding the influence of physical facilities, service quality, and human resource competency on satisfaction with logistics facility services at the OJK Head Office, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Physical facilities have a positive and significant impact on satisfaction with logistics services at the OJK Head Office. This indicates that comfortable, adequate, and supportive physical facilities can increase the satisfaction of internal service users.
2. Service quality has a positive and significant impact on satisfaction with logistics facilities at the OJK Head Office. This indicates that service accuracy, response speed, and service reliability are important factors in increasing user satisfaction.
3. Human resource competency has a positive and significant impact on satisfaction with logistics facility services at the OJK Head Office. This indicates that employee competency in providing professional and communicative services can increase service satisfaction for internal users.
4. The physical facility variable is the variable that has the most dominant influence on satisfaction with logistics facility services within the OJK Head Office environment.

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